

PROVISION OF PUBLIC PRACTICES IN THE DIGITAL AGE GOVERNMENT

Abdul Halil Hi. Ibrahim *¹

Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara
chalilibrahim101@gmail.com

Iksan R.A. Arsad

Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara
iksanra@gmail.com

Rasid Pora

Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara
porarasid@gmail.com

Abstract

The digital age has brought significant changes to the global social, economic, and political order, deeply affecting the structure and functioning of public policy. The study aims to dig into the dynamics of public policy in the digital age of governance, assessing the approaches, influences, and implications of such transformations on the maintenance of government and public service. By adopting methods of literary research, the study provides in-depth analysis of how digital technology has been used to improve efficiency, transparency, and participation in public policy processes, as well as identifying emerging challenges and opportunities. The results of this study show that governments in various parts of the world have undertaken a number of initiatives to incorporate digital technology into their public policy strategies, resulting in significant improvements in terms of service access, service quality, and public participation and engagement. However, challenges such as digital gaps, cybersecurity, and personal data protection need to be overcome to maximize the benefits of public policy in the digital age.

Keywords: Dynamics, Public Policy, Government, Digital Age.

Introduction

The development of digital technology has taken place at an incredible rate, affecting almost every aspect of life, including the way government is run. This trend not only changes the traditional paradigm regarding the maintenance of public services, but also redefines the relationship between government and society. (Hariguna et al., 2021).

The system of government is more transparent and accountable to the public. Social media, government websites, and open data portals, make it easier for citizens to access information about policies, programmes, and decisions made by

¹ Correspondence author

governments. This not only increases public confidence, but also facilitates public monitoring of government performance (Dal Bó et al., 2021).

Online platforms and mobile applications offer channels for citizens to convey their opinions, participate in public consultations, and interact directly with policymakers. This opens up an opportunity for governments to gain valuable feedback and enhance the support base for their programmes and policies. (Ren et al., 2021).

So with that, advances in information and communication technology have changed the way government entities interact with society, as well as in formulating and implementing their policies. From paper-based administration to transparent e-government systems, digital governance has become a must in creating efficient, fast, and responsive governance to public needs (Ahmad et al., 2021; Dal Bó et al, 2021).

Public policy as a key instrument in responding to social challenges is now also faced with the complex dynamics resulting from these technological developments. Public policy is directed to take advantage of opportunities as well as address the challenges posed by the rapid development of digital technologies. Governments around the world are taking proactive steps to integrate digital technology in public services, protecting data privacy, and empowering the digital economy (Ehrenberg et al., 2021). Public policies towards the digital age generally cover several aspects such as Digital Infrastructure Development, E-Government Maintenance, Data Protection and Privacy, Cyber Security, Digital Economy Empowerment, Education and Digital Skills, and Digital Inclusion. (Hill, M., & Hupe, P. 2021).

Public policy in the digital age requires an integrated approach that utilizes technology for sustainable development. Its implementation should be based on a sustainable assessment of the social, economic, and environmental impacts of digital technologies, ensuring that such policies are adaptable to future technological developments. (Hill, M., & Varone, F. 2021).

Public policy adjustment in the digital age is a very important and urgent step to help countries respond quickly and effectively to the significant and rapid changes taking place in society and the economy. So, Public Policy Adjustments in the Digital Age is not just a matter for governments, but also requires the active participation of stakeholders from the private sector, academics, and civil society, to ensure inclusive and sustainable development. (Hill, M., & Varone, F. 2021; Kraft, M. E., & Furlong, S. R. 2019; Ahmad et al., 2021).

Thus, there is an urgent need to understand how public policy dynamics are shaped in the context of today's digital age. Detecting and analyzing the challenges and opportunities emerging from the integration of technology into policy processes is crucial to optimizing the potential of digital technology in creating more inclusive, effective, and innovative public policies.

The study aims to uncover and analyze the dynamics of public policy in the context of governance in the digital age, focusing on identifying challenges,

opportunities, and adaptation strategies in policy making and implementation. The study also aims at providing strategic recommendations for policymakers to improve the quality and effectiveness of policy in a digital age. The research will adopt a theoretical framework that involves Public Policy Theory to understand the process of policymaking and implementing, Digital Governance Theory in tackling technological change, as well as Innovation in Government Theory as a basis in identifying and analyzing policy innovation opportunities in the Digital Age.

Research Method

The method of literary research is the method of research conducted by collecting, identifying, compiling, and analyzing data published in the form of books, journal articles, and other sources relevant to a given research topic. This can include previous empirical research, relevant theories, as well as practical applications related to the topic. (Champe & Kleist, 2003; Tharenou et al., 2007).

The literature research process carried out by the researcher begins with the search for relevant keywords in the database and catalogue to identify material that matches the scope of the research problem. From there, researchers can read and record important information, and then manage research materials that have been collected to compile comprehensive literature reviews. (Basrowi, 2008; Zed, 2004).

The study of literature allows researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of the historical context, key theories, methodologies, and research results related to the topic they are exploring. In addition, it also helps in establishing the theoretical foundations for research, as well as identifying gaps in literature that can be explored for further research. (Sugiyono, 2010; Ferdinand, 2014).

Result and Discussion

Public policy in the digital age

Public policy in the Digital Age refers to strategies and decisions made by governments to regulate, facilitate, and direct the use of digital technology in an effort to solve public problems and improve the quality of services to the public. (Waluyo, D. 2022). This includes the use of big data, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and other technologies in decision-making, provision of public services, and interaction with citizens. The digital age has changed the face of public policy around the world, bringing new challenges and opportunities in how policies are designed, implemented, and monitored for their effectiveness in an increasingly digitally connected society. (Tasyah et al., 2021).

The scope of public policy in the digital age covers several critical aspects, including the development of information technology infrastructure, regulations and legal frameworks that support the digital economy, the digitization of public services, as well as cybersecurity and the protection of personal data. In the digital era,

policymakers are faced with the need to integrate new technologies into the maintenance of government and the provision of services to citizens quickly and efficiently. (Mariyati, T. 2013).

In addition, public policies in the digital age also include empowering citizens in a digital economy, including supporting digital skills and information literacy that enable wider citizen participation in the economy and democracy. It involves initiatives to improve access and affordability of technology, as well as developing an ecosystem that drives innovation and entrepreneurship in the field of digital technology. (Saputro, R. H. 2021; Jayadi, L. I. 2023).

Digital Governance

Digital governance, or also known as Digital Government, can be understood as an effort to modernize public services through the adoption of digital technology. It opens up opportunities for governments in serving the public as well as increasing public participation and collaboration in the creation of appropriate services. Furthermore, Digital Government or e-government is the use of information technology by the government to provide information and services to its citizens, to deal with business affairs, as well as to streamline various matters relating to government. (Pakhnenko, O., & Kuan, Z. 2023).

In an effort to understand the component of digital governance, several key elements involved can determine the success of the implementation of digital government. One source defines the key components of digital Governance including the coverage and quality of the digital government services, the status of the development of digital infrastructure, and the efficiency of human resources in operating e-government services. Other components that support digital governance are solid policies, effective institutions, technical frameworks, and infrastructure, as well as security and privacy aspects. (Yuan et al., 2023).

More specifically, these components include: 1) Information Technology Infrastructure: This component covers the hardware, software, networks, and data facilities needed to host government digital services. 2) Public Policy: Developing policies that support digital transformation in government, including regulations governing e-commerce, e-government, and other related aspects. 3) Institutions: Structures and organizations in government entrusted with implementing and managing digital services; 4) Human Resources: Including training and development of technical capabilities of government officials in using and administering information technology. 5) Cybersecurity and Privacy: Security mechanisms to protect data and information from cyber attacks and provide privacy for users of services. (Castilla et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2023).

The implementation of digital governance aims to create transparent, participatory, and efficient governance through the use of technology. The above-mentioned components play a role in ensuring that public services are faster, easier, and accessible to all segments of society.

Implementing digital governance is a complex process involving a wide range of stakeholders, institutional setting, and technology adoption. The following are the common stages or steps undertaken in the implementation of digital governance: 1) Preparation of a Strategic Plan: Establishing the vision, mission, and objectives to be achieved from digital government, as well as planning strategies to those objectives. 2) IT Infrastructure Development: Development or improvement of adequate information technology infrastructure such as high-speed internet networks, data centers, and other digital platforms. 3) Application and Services Development: Build or adapt applications for the provision of public services online, including government portals, e-filing systems, online payments, etc. 4) Regulations and Regulations: Develop and review policies, regulations, and laws that support the implementation of digital governance, protect personal data, and ensure cyber security. 5) System Integration: Integrate systems in various government institutions to create a well-integrated system and avoid duplication. 6) Development of SDM Capacity: Conduct training and development to enhance the capacity of human resources including government officials in the use of digital tools and services. 7) Application of Cybersecurity: Build strong security systems to protect data and services from potential cyber threats. 8) Implementation and Operational: Starting the implementation of digital services and operating them, responding to the need for continuous updating and maintenance. 9) Evaluation and Sustainable Improvement: Conducting an evaluation of the digital services that have been implemented and carrying out continuous improvements to improve the quality of services. 10) Increasing Public Participation: Increase public awareness and use of digital service amongst the public and encourage public participation through feedback or co-creation initiatives. 11) Collaboration and Partnerships: Develop partnerships with the private sector, academics, and the community for innovation and improvement of services needed by the community. 12) Monitoring and Reporting: Develop monitoring and reporting systems to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of services provided as well as progress in the implementation of digital governance. (Zhao et al., 2023; Sanina et al., 2023).

Success in implementing digital governance requires good change management, support from leaders at all levels, as well as the active involvement of stakeholders, including civil society and the private sector.

Digital governance, despite its many advantages, also faces a number of significant challenges during its implementation process. Some of the major challenges in implementing digital governance include: 1) Infrastructure and limited Internet access: In regions with underdeveloped infrastructure, the difficulty of accessing the

Internet with adequate speed and bandwidth can be a major obstacle. 2) Data security and privacy: Ensuring the security of citizens' personal information and government data from cyber attacks is a significant challenge. Layered security approaches and periodic technology updates are essential to gaining public confidence. 3) Digital Literacy and Public Awareness: Not all societies have the skills or convenience to use digital technology, which demands inclusive education and training programmes. 4) Cultural Management Change and Resistance: Changing the way of work that has long been embedded in government institutions can raise resistance from officials, which requires strong change management and leadership. 5) Regulation and Policy: Creating and modernizing regulations that support digital transformation often takes time and can be complex, especially in terms of finding a balance between innovation and user protection. 6) System Integration: Integrating IT systems that are already running in various government departments into one integrated system is often challenging due to interoperability and legacy systems. 7) Providing a Service tailored to the needs of the User: Developing a digital service that truly meets user needs requires a good understanding of user experience and service design. 8) Insufficient Resources: Budget constraints, human resources, and technical skills can hinder the initiation and sustainability of digital governance projects. 9) Socialization and Adoption: Encouraging the adoption and use of digital services by the general public can be a challenge, especially among those less familiar with technology. 10) Dependency on External Vendors: Dependence on software solutions and services provided by third parties can create cost-related risks, sustainability, and innovation constraints if not properly managed. 11) Growing cyber security threats: Growing levels of cyber threats require continuous monitoring and updating of information security systems. 12) Service Disclosure: Ensure that all community groups benefit equally from digital government services, including vulnerable and marginalized groups (Gong, Y., & Li, X. 2023; Martins, J., & Veiga, L. G. 2022).

To address these challenges, a holistic approach is needed that includes cross-sectoral cooperation, investment in human resource capacity, improved IT infrastructure, and active participation of the public.

Public Policy Opportunities in the Digital Age

The digital age has opened up opportunities for improving and renewing public policies in various fields. Here are some of the public policy opportunities that can be exploited during the digital transformation: 1) Improving the efficiency of public services, including; a) Process Automation: Using automated systems to accelerate administrative processes. b) Digital platforms: Developing applications or websites to facilitate access to public services such as licensing, education, and health. 2) Transparency and accountability, including. a) Open data: Widening access to open data that can enhance transparency, drive innovation, and research., b) Real-time

dashboards: Implementing real-time Dashboards for monitoring government agency performance and budget allocation. 3) Digital participation and democracy, including; (a) E-voting and E-petition: Enabling citizens to vote and file petitions online to increase political participation. (b) Online forums: Creating forums or discussion platforms to listen to input and facilitate dialogue between government and public. 4) Economic development and empowerment, including; (a) the digital economy: boosting economic growth through investment in the IT and startup sectors; (b) digital education: expanding access and quality of education through e-learning platforms and digital curricula. 5) Decentralization and Regional Services, including; (a) Regional Information Systems: Development of integrated information systems for local government, improving coordination and efficiency of services. (b) Digital village: Empowerment of villages through digital village projects that support local technology-based initiatives. 6) Data Security and Protection, including; (a) Data Regulation: Strengthening regulations on personal data protection and cybersecurity; (b) Security Systems: Investing in digital security infrastructure to protect data and public information systems from cyber threats; (7) Inclusion and Social Justice, inclusive; (a) Inclusive digital services: Developing digital services that are accessible to all segments of society, including marginalized groups and persons with disabilities; (b) Digital Literacy: Digital literacy programmes to enhance the ability of the population to use technology. 8) Health and Welfare, including; (a) Telemedicine: Introducing and developing remote health services; (b) Population health databases: Managing population health data to improve health policies and services; (9) Sustainability and the Environment of Life, inclusive; (i) Smart cities: Implementing smart city concepts for more efficient and sustainable city resource management and infrastructure; (ii) Tech-green initiatives: Creating policies that support environmentally friendly technology innovation. 10) Data-based analysis and decision-making, including; (a) Big data analytics: Using big data for policy analysis and evidence-based decision making; (b) AI and Machine Learning: Integrating AI into government for trend prediction and policy automation. (Alfaro-Ponce et al., 2023; Gong, Y., & Li, X. 2023; Suparno, S., & Kamuli, S. 2023).

The successful implementation of these policies depends on cooperation between the public and private sectors, the provision of adequate resources, and strong support from the public. Developing national capacity, infrastructure, and digital literacy is vital in supporting all of the above initiatives. (Idzi, F. M., & Gomes, R. C. 2022).

Conclusion

The dynamics of public policy in the governance of the digital age mark an important transition from conventional methods to more innovative, efficient, and inclusive approaches. These changes are brought about by rapid technological advances, changing the way governments interact with their citizens, manage

resources, and provide services. Here are the key conclusions on the dynamics of public policy in the digital age of governance: 1) More efficient provision of services: Digital technology allows governments to simplify processes, reduce bureaucracy, and accelerate the delivery of public services, making it more accessible to the public. 2) Transparency and Accountability: Digitalization facilitates wider access to public information, increases transparency in decision-making processes, and strengthens government responsibility. 3) Public participation: Digital platforms create new spaces for public participation, enabling citizens to contribute to government policy development and monitoring in real-time. 4) Data-based decision making: Advances in big data and analytics provide essential tools for governments to make evidence-based decisions, predict future trends, and proactively respond to public needs. 5) Adapting to Economic Change: The digital age requires policies that support the digital economy, including innovation, entrepreneurship, and digital competence, to boost economic growth and national competitiveness. 6) Protection in the Maya World: The issue of cybersecurity and personal data protection is becoming increasingly critical, urging governments to develop strong regulations, infrastructure, and response mechanisms to protect individuals and national interests. 7) Equality and Inclusion: Digital technology provides an opportunity to reduce gaps and expand access to services to marginal groups and remote areas, but also requires proactive policies to prevent the emergence of digital gaps. 8) Health and Welfare: The COVID-19 pandemic emphasizes the importance of digital technology in providing health services, from telemedicine to health information management, inviting innovation in public health policy. 9) Sustainability and Environment: Digital technologies offer new tools to address environmental challenges, from monitoring natural resources to developing smarter cities that are more sustainable. 10) Exclusion: Ensuring that all layers of society benefit equally from digital transformation is a challenge that public policy must address, ensuring that no one is left behind in this change.

In conclusion, the dynamics of public policy in the digital age drive governments to be more adaptive, responsive, and innovative in responding to rapid socio-economic changes. Adoption and integration of digital technology into public policy is key to addressing current and future challenges, while maximizing benefits for society.

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